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REVIEW ON THE RESEARCH PAPER WRITTEN BY DIVYA MISHRA “*THAT LONG SILENCE*” NOVEL BY SHASHI DESHPANDE”

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Divya Mishra is a research scholar At Allahabad University. Ms. Mishra has taken into account the feminist point to write this paper. She studies the Deshpande’s psychological insight into the Indian Women’s behavior. This novel fetched Booker prize to the writer. The title “The Long Silence” compliments the protagonist, Jaya Kulkarni, who keeps silence throughout her life.

The novel analyses the human relationships through the institution of marriage. The marriages collapse or end due to lack of understanding, lack of commitment and dedication. Egos and aspirations are also the reasons for the marriages to discontinue. This novel is critical analysis of the institution known as marriage. It also analyses the mindset of a woman who goes through the pain of breaking down when a relationship, a marriage comes to an end. The woman’s life got entangled between conservative thoughts, patriarchy, suppression, and terror. The protagonist of the novel represents the Indian women who want to break the silence created around them by male hegemony.

According to Ms. Mishra, the protagonist represents those kinds of women who are trapped between modernism and traditional behavior. Like a normal woman she is also trained as a perfect wife who never questions her husband. One of her aunt even taught her so much so that one can think that it is a patriarchal society. Whatever a husband does water it as a flourishing tree if you want a shelter underneath it. Even if husband keeps a mistress, she has to compromise. These type of teachings show that how much women suffered for decades and centuries.

I think these sufferings, anguish, pain and agony made all these women to revolt and fight for their rights. Now the women are more independent, rebellious, defiant and bold. No doubt the term became a rage all these years.

WORK CITED

1. Mishra, Divya. " The Theme of Silence in Shashi Deshpande's That Long Silence." *IJOHMN (International Journal online of Humanities)* [Online], 2.3 (2016): n. pag. Web. 09.Sep. 2018